

FIRDAVSI'S WORK "SHAHNOMA" AND UZBEK FOLKLORE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11185257>

Abstract

Language teaching and learning programs provide students the opportunity to discover how languages are learned and how they may be most-effectively taught. These programs allow students to consider questions including the subsequent: What theoretical troubles underline the teaching and studying of language?

Key words: language, learning, teaching, second language, communication, speech, human behavior, expression, synonyms of language.

Getting to know a second language is a protracted and complicated venture. Your complete individual is affected as you conflict to attain past the confines of your first language and into a new language, a new lifestyle, a brand new way of questioning, feeling, and appearing. Overall commitment, general involvement, a complete physical, intellectual. And emotional reaction is essential to efficiently send and receive messages in a second language. Many variables are worried in the acquisition process. Language mastering isn't a fixed of smooth steps that can be programmed in a brief do-it-yourself package. So much is at stake that courses in overseas languages are often inadequate education grounds, in and of themselves, for the success learning of a 2d language. Few if any human beings achieve fluency in a foreign language solely inside the confines of the lecture room. It is able to seem contradictory, then, that this eBook is about both gaining knowledge of and coaching. however some of the contradiction is removed if you have a look at the coaching process as the facilitation of getting to know, wherein you may educate an overseas language correctly if, among other matters, you realize something approximately that tricky net of variables that are spun together to have an effect on how and why one learns or falls to research a 2d language.

LANGUAGE

Language is using a system of communicate which consists of a set of sounds or written symbols. College students tested how youngsters collect language. Language isn't artwork but each is styles of human conduct. Synonyms: speech,

communicate, expression, talking extra synonyms of language. Styles of language: Expressive language: How infants talk to others thru increasingly more sophisticated speech and improved vocabulary. Pragmatic language: all the subtle facets of language – facial expressions, body, moves, tone, extent, inflection, thoughts about whilst to speak and for how lengthy. This kind that helps you to examine. Due to the fact this is conversation of human beings. This is a vital part. A definition is a statement captures the important thing features of an idea. Those capabilities may additionally vary, relying for your own (or the lexicographer's) know-how of the construct. And, most crucial, that know-how is basically a "principle" that explicates the assemble. So a definition of a term can be notion of as a condensed version of a concept. Conversely, a concept is really—or now not so certainly—an extended definition. Defining, dicrefore is critical commercial enterprise: it calls for choices about which aspects of something are worthy of being included. Assume you were stopped by means of a reporter on the street, and inside the route of an interview about your field of examine, you have been requested: "nicely, because you're interested by second language acquisition, please define language in a sentence or two." you will absolute confidence dig deep into your reminiscence for a typical dictionary-kind definition of language. Such definitions, if pursued seriously, may want to lead to a lexicographer's wild-goose chase, however they can also mirror a fairly coherent synopsis of cutting-edge information of simply what its miles that linguists are seeking to study.

Gaining knowledge of AND teaching

We also can ask questions about constructs like getting to know and coaching. Recollect once more some conventional definitions. A seek in current dictionaries exhibits that getting to know is "acquiring or getting of understanding of a subject or a skill via look at, experience, or instruction." learning, and coaching of mastering, may be described as "showing or helping a person to learn how to do something, giving instructions, guiding inside the observe of something, supplying with information, causing to recognize or apprehend." isn't it curious that professional lexicographers seem to have such issue in devising a definition of something as prevalent as coaching? Extra than perhaps anything else, such definitions reflect the issue of defining complicated principles. Breaking down the components of the definition of learning, we can extract, as we did with language, domains of research and inquiry;

1. Learning is acquisition or "getting."
2. Studying is retention of records or skill.

3. Retention implies storage structures, reminiscence, and cognitive organization.
4. Getting to know includes lively, aware awareness on and performing upon activities outdoor or inside the organism.
5. Gaining knowledge of is especially permanent but issue to forgetting.
6. Mastering entails a few shape of practice, possibly reinforced practice.
7. Gaining knowledge of is a trade in behavior. Those principles can also supply manner to a number of subfields inside the area of psychology: acquisition procedures. Perception, memory (storage) systems, short- and lengthy-time period memory, take into account, motivation, aware and unconscious getting to know styles and techniques, theories of forgetting, reinforcement, the role of exercise. in no time the idea of gaining knowledge of will become every bit as complex because the concept of language. Yet the second language learner brings these types of (and greater) variables into play within the getting to know of a second language. Coaching can't be described aside from studying. Coaching is guiding and facilitating getting to know, enabling the learner to examine, placing the conditions for getting to know. Your understanding of ways the learner learns will decide your philosophy of training, your coaching style, your technique, methods, and classroom strategies. A idea of teaching, in concord together with your incorporated understanding of the learner and of the challenge remember to be found out, will factor the way to successful tactics on a given day for given newbies beneath the numerous constraints of the unique context of getting to know. In different phrases, your principle of teaching is your concept of mastering "stood on its head."

Conclusion

As you see, those types of strategies that could assist to study 2d language. Now, we discussed approximately them. We assume you may recognize this technique. Simplest your activities can't assist you, however also you must understand these kinds of techniques, techniques, elements. With one word gaining knowledge of 2d language this is difficult and smooth. It depends in your plan and activities. But you don't accept as true with any styles of methods, improvements. Because all of them that are not development. Abstract: This article analyzes the similarities between "Shahnoma" and folk tales "Rustamkhan", and "Alpomish" and the birth of Goroguli.

Key words: "Shahnoma", Rustamkhan, Adil king, Images of Zahhok, Faridun, Shirin and Khusrav, Farhad.

In folklore, there are warnings that our forefathers wanted to tell, the requirements of being a respected person, the bravery of great children of the country, such as Alp Ertonga, Tomaris, Shiroq, Jaloliddin Manguberdi, Temur Malik, the traditions of our people, and sayings that have risen to the level of art about our national qualities. , finds its expression in examples of songs, fairy tales, epics, children's works, and other genres. That's why it was customary to call folk art a national value.

Folk art is called folklore in science. This term was proposed by the English scientist William Thoms in 1846, and its meaning is the concept of "people's wisdom". Folklore means all the art examples created by the people. Examples of architecture, painting, jewelry, goldsmithing, music, dance, and oral literature are all accepted as folklore. Every specialist working in the field of art calls his chosen term "folklore". For example, a musician considers folk tunes, a choreographer folk dances, an architect folk architecture, a folklorist scientist folk epics and fairy tales as works of folklore.

As we work in the field of studying the secrets of the art of words, we record and analyze proverbs, riddles, praises, anecdotes, songs, fairy tales, and epics as examples of folklore. When we pronounce the term "folklore", we understand the oral creation of the people. A scientist who studies folklore is a folklorist. Folklore is now a part of literary studies. Fiction begins with folklore. Therefore, the first part of the history of literature is folklore. Therefore, students of the Faculty of Philology begin the process of formation as specialists by studying folklore. Folklore is the basis of speech art.

At the same time, folklore works are always connected with live performances. Therefore, fairy tales, songs, epics, and several other works of oral creativity are examples of syncretic art during performance. The word syncretic means to unite, to mix, to mix. When the epic is sung, music, words, and performing arts mix and harmonize. That is, he sings a story in a pleasant voice as a singer, playing a dulcimer. The epic consists of text - words, and because it is performed on a musical instrument, it becomes a song and a musician. At the same time, the events of the saga are narrated with sound recording - stage art - acting skills.

As a result, a sample of syncretic art is created. Also, dancing and stage actions are performed during the performance of songs or works related to folk drama. Therefore, as the basis of the work being performed is the word, we cannot imagine its presentation to the audience without connection with other forms of art. So, we can say that most of the art forms that have become

complicated today appeared, formed, developed, and later became a unique art form in the process of performing works of folk art at the initial stage. , we will not make such a big mistake.

The great poet Abulqasim Firdavsi was born into a poor family in the city of Tus, Khorasan region. However, this work was not appreciated enough by Mahmud Ghaznavi. The Shahnama is the masterpiece of the great Persian-Tajik poet Abulqasim Firdaws. Firdaws rewrote the work "Shahnama" based on the narratives that existed in Sogd and during the Sassanid Empire. The stories in the work are written in the author's language.

"Shahnoma" contains legends woven by ancient tribes, heroic epics, and the history of Iran and Central Asia from the time of Alexander the Great until the Arab invasion, i.e. until the death of the last Sassanid king Yazdigird. is a chronicle. The Uzbek people have been honoring the work of "Shahnoma" and Firdaws for a long time. Because the original work and its various translations are loved by our people until now, the work "Shahnoma" was translated into Uzbek in 1682 by Mulla Khomush Akhun Khomushi. The work promotes the ideas of glorifying the values of the people, expressing the eternal and eternal struggle between good and evil, glorifying the motherland, and showing off the power of the people.

Although the author lived in 934 years, he aims to show the conquerors in his territory that he also has a great history. "Farhod and Shirin", which has existed in folklore since ancient times, and it is unknown when it was created, in "Birth of Goroguli" in "Birth of Goroguli" to save the son of Mari, the fate of the characters in the epic "Alpomish and Ravshan", the fate of the characters, the development of events, are reminiscent of these aspects in "Shahnoma". So, "Shahnoma" received spiritual nourishment from folk oral works. "Shahnoma" has many similarities with folk epics.

For example: in "Shahnoma" Kaikovus avenges his son to Ahriman and in "Birth of Goroguli" Adil sends an army to the king of the land of Mari to save his son Ravshan. When Zahhok sees how he is killed in a dream, the fate of the heroes in the epic "Alpomish" and "Ravshan" becomes clear in a dream. If Faridun and his mother live on Mount Elbrus, in the epic "Rustamkhan" Rustamkhan and his mother live on Mount Hukumi. If we see in the interpretation of the characters of Firdaws's "Shahnoma" and Amir Khusrav Dehlavi's "Shirin and Khusrav", the love between Khusrav and Shirin appears in written fiction for the first time in Firdavsi's "Shahnoma". . The character of Farhad in Firdausi's work is the general of Khusrav, and his closeness to Shirin

in the love chapter is not based on the dream. Farhad's image is further improved in Amir Khusrav Dehlavi's epic "Shirin and Khusrav". He is now depicted as a prince, the son of the Khan of Chin.

Zahhok, who took over the kingdom with the conspiracy of Ahriman and has been the owner of the crown for a thousand years, bleeds the people of the country and takes care of the snakes growing from his shoulders with their brains. But in Firdausi's imagination, it was unnatural for a blacksmith to lead a newly established country. That is why he pays special attention to the fact that Faridun, the son of Jamshid, became the ruler of the kingdom instead of Zahhok and that during his reign, Faridun was a righteous king.

The conclusion is that while reading Abulqasim Firdausi's Shahnama, we can call this work a royal work. The work of Shahnama includes legends, narratives, and heroic epics woven by ancient tribes. Our people have revered Firdausi and the work "Shahnoma" for a long time, and the work "Shohnoma" is read with love by our people.

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